

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Adjustment criteria

Table S1. Formulas and recommendations for fit indexes.

Fit index	Formula	Recommendation
χ^2	$\chi^2 = (N - 1)\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$	non-significance supports the model.
SRMR	$\text{SRMR} = \sqrt{\frac{\left\{2 \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^i [(s_{ij} - \hat{\sigma}_{ij}) / (s_{ii}s_{jj})]^2\right\}}{p(p+1)}}$	≤ 0.05 suggests a good fit (close fit); ≤ 0.08 suggests an adequate fit; ≥ 0.10 suggests a poor fit.
CFI	$\text{CFI} = 1 - \frac{\max[(T_T - df_T), 0]}{\max[(T_T - df_T), (T_B - df_B), 0]}$	≥ 0.95 suggests a good fit; ≥ 0.90 suggests an adequate fit.
TLI	$\text{TLI} = \frac{\left(\frac{T_B}{df_B}\right) - \left(\frac{T_T}{df_T}\right)}{\left(\frac{T_B}{df_B}\right) - 1}$	≥ 0.95 suggests a good fit; ≥ 0.90 suggests an adequate fit.

χ^2 is chi-squared test; N is the sample size; $\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the fit function from maximum likelihood; s_{ij} is the observed covariances; $\hat{\sigma}_{ij}$ is the reproduced covariances; s_{ii} and s_{jj} are the observed standard deviations; T_B is the T statistic for the baseline model; df_B is the degree of freedom of baseline model; T_T is the T statistic for the target model; df_T is the degree of freedom of target model.

Convergence analysis for MTM model

Table S2. Lags and Autocorrelations for genetic chain

	Lag1	Lag5	Lag10	Lag50
V1	0.2084	-0.0008	0.0015	0.0019
V2	0.1977	0.0036	-0.0028	-0.0053
V3	0.1738	0.0024	-0.0020	-0.0055
V4	0.1487	0.0009	-0.0016	-0.0050
V5	0.1280	0.0023	0.0056	-0.0050

V6	0.1148	0.0022	0.0054	-0.0038
V7	0.1020	0.0013	0.0042	-0.0023
V8	0.0934	0.0020	0.0042	-0.0021
V9	0.0787	0.0005	0.0038	-0.0007
V10	0.0585	-0.0021	0.0011	-0.0007

Table S3. Geweke Convergence Diagnostic for genetic chain considering fraction in first window = 0.1 and fraction in last window = 0.5

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10
Z-	0.7	0.0	-0.	-1.	-1.	-1.	-1.	-1.	-1.	-1.
Score	955	249	7347	0680	7515	7361	7520	5679	9714	7976
p-	0.4	0.9	0.4	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0
value	263	801	625	855	799	825	798	169	487	722

Table S4. Lags and Autocorrelations for residual chain

	Lag 1	Lag 5	Lag 10	Lag 50
V1	0.0777	0.0038	0.0008	0.0009
V2	0.1803	0.0028	0.0010	-0.0036
V3	0.1662	0.0010	0.0032	-0.0035
V4	0.1418	0.0022	0.0010	-0.0008
V5	0.0512	-0.0003	-0.0014	-0.0013
V6	0.0395	-0.0010	-0.0024	-0.0032
V7	0.0437	0.0002	-0.0007	-0.0003
V8	0.0339	0.0000	-0.0031	-0.0037
V9	0.0418	0.0003	0.0004	-0.0014
V10	0.0571	0.0020	0.0021	-0.0002

Table S5. Geweke Convergence Diagnostic for residual chain considering fraction in first window = 0.1 and fraction in last window = 0.5

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10
Z-	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	1.3	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.8
Score	568	730	426	693	26	267	424	520	038	108
p-	0.87	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
value	54	418	866	448	848	038	005	798	884	702

Convergence analysis for SEM model

Table S6. Lags and Autocorrelations for genetic chain

	Lag1	Lag5	Lag10	Lag50
V1	0.6737	0.1749	0.0520	0.0187
V2	0.6853	0.1821	0.0354	-0.0330
V3	0.7208	0.2277	0.0770	0.0065
V4	0.6738	0.1679	0.0263	0.0130
V5	0.6362	0.1077	0.0060	-0.0243
V6	0.6663	0.1684	0.0239	0.0110
V7	0.6411	0.1169	0.0084	0.0128
V8	0.6845	0.2005	0.0453	0.0223
V9	0.6815	0.1810	0.0507	-0.0046
V10	0.5960	0.0917	0.0489	-0.0073

Table S7. Geweke Convergence Diagnostic for genetic chain considering fraction in first window = 0.1 and fraction in last window = 0.5

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10
Z-Score	0.7	-0.	-0.	-0.	-1.	-0.	-0.	-1.	-1.	0.7
Score	955	2442	8888	9016	7733	2574	3036	3742	2129	015
p-value	0.4	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.7	0.7	0.1	0.2	0.4
	263	071	741	672	762	969	615	694	252	830

Table S8. Lags and Autocorrelations for residual chain

	Lag 1	Lag 5	Lag 10	Lag 50
V1	0.0777	0.0038	0.0008	0.0009
V2	0.0381	0.0001	-0.0023	-0.0008
V3	0.0063	-0.0004	0.0014	0.0008
V4	-0.0010	-0.0054	0.0053	-0.0029

Table S9. Geweke Convergence Diagnostic for residual chain considering fraction in first window = 0.1 and fraction in last window = 0.5

	V1	V2	V3	V4
Z-Score	-0.1568	1.5161	-0.0442	1.6885
p-value	0.8754	0.1295	0.9647	0.0913

Algebraic calculations for genetic and residual parameters

Text S1. Algebraic calculations for genetic and residual parameters

According to the SEM model developed for the case of mixed linear models, as shown below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{YL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{VL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{NL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{LLL} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & I \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} & I \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & I \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \\ 0 & I \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} & 0 & I \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{YL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{VL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{NL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{LLL} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{YL} \\ \mathbf{g}_{VL} \\ \mathbf{g}_{NL} \\ \mathbf{g}_{LLL} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{YL} \\ \mathbf{e}_{VL} \\ \mathbf{e}_{NL} \\ \mathbf{e}_{LLL} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where $[\mathbf{y}_{YL} \ \mathbf{y}_{VL} \ \mathbf{y}_{NL} \ \mathbf{y}_{LLL}]^t$ represents the vector of phenotypes, $\mathbf{\Lambda} =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & I\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \\ 0 & I\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} & 0 & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$
 is a matrix of structural coefficients,

$[\mathbf{g}_{YL} \ \mathbf{g}_{VL} \ \mathbf{g}_{NL} \ \mathbf{g}_{LLL}]^t$ is the vector of additive genetic effects, and

$[\mathbf{e}_{YL} \ \mathbf{e}_{VL} \ \mathbf{e}_{NL} \ \mathbf{e}_{LLL}]^t$ is the vector of residuals. The vectors \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{e} follow a joint

distribution $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g} \\ \mathbf{e} \end{bmatrix} = N\left\{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{\Sigma}_g \otimes \mathbf{G} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{\Psi} \otimes \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}\right\}$, where $\mathbf{\Sigma}_g$ and $\mathbf{\Psi}$ are the additive genetic and residual covariance matrices, respectively.

According to Gianola and Sorensen (2004), the SEM model can be simplified, provided that $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1}$ exists, as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{YL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{VL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{NL} \\ \mathbf{y}_{LLL} \end{bmatrix} = \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & I\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \\ 0 & I\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} & 0 & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{YL} \\ \mathbf{g}_{VL} \\ \mathbf{g}_{NL} \\ \mathbf{g}_{LLL} \end{bmatrix} +$$

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & I\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \\ 0 & I\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} & 0 & I\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{YL} \\ \mathbf{e}_{VL} \\ \mathbf{e}_{NL} \\ \mathbf{e}_{LLL} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{YL}^* \\ \mathbf{g}_{VL}^* \\ \mathbf{g}_{NL}^* \\ \mathbf{g}_{LLL}^* \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{YL}^* \\ \mathbf{e}_{VL}^* \\ \mathbf{e}_{NL}^* \\ \mathbf{e}_{LLL}^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

where the vectors \mathbf{g}^* and \mathbf{e}^* follow a joint distribution $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g}^* \\ \mathbf{e}^* \end{bmatrix} = N\left\{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{\Sigma}_g^* \otimes \mathbf{G} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{\Psi}^* \otimes \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}\right\}$,

where $\mathbf{\Sigma}_g^*$ and $\mathbf{\Psi}^*$ are the additive genetic and residual covariance matrices, respectively.

With this model, the phenotypic value for each variable can be described as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{YL} &= \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} y_{LLL} + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} y_{NL} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} y_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} y_{LLL} + \\ &\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} y_{LLL} + g_{YL} + e_{YL} = \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} (g_{LLL} + e_{LLL}) + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} (g_{NL} + e_{NL}) + \\ &\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} (g_{VL} + e_{VL}) + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} (g_{LLL} + e_{LLL}) + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} (g_{LLL} + \\ &e_{LLL}) + (g_{YL} + e_{YL}) = (\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} g_{LLL} + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{NL} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{VL} + \end{aligned}$$

$$\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{LLL} + g_{YL}) + (\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} e_{LLL} + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} e_{NL} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} e_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} e_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} e_{LLL} + e_{YL}) = g_{YL}^* + e_{YL}^*, \quad (18)$$

$$y_{VL} = \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} y_{LLL} + g_{VL} + e_{VL} = (\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} g_{LLL} + e_{LLL}) + (g_{VL} + e_{VL}) = (\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} g_{LLL} + g_{VL}) + (\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} e_{LLL} + e_{VL}) = g_{VL}^* + e_{VL}^*, \quad (19)$$

$$y_{NL} = \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} y_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} y_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} y_{LLL} + g_{NL} + e_{NL} = \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} (g_{VL} + e_{VL}) + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} (g_{LLL} + e_{LLL}) + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} (g_{LLL} + e_{LLL}) + g_{NL} + e_{NL} = (\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} g_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} g_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} g_{LLL} + g_{NL}) + (\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} e_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} e_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} e_{LLL} + e_{NL}) = g_{NL}^* + e_{NL}^*, \quad (20)$$

$$y_{LLL} = g_{LLL} + e_{LLL} = g_{LLL}^* + e_{LLL}^*. \quad (21)$$

The covariances between the genetic effects can be estimated as follows:

$$\sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}}^* = \text{COV}(g_{LLL}^*, g_{VL}^*) = \text{COV}(g_{LLL}, \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} g_{LLL} + g_{VL}) = \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}}, \quad (22)$$

$$\sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{NL}}^* = \text{COV}(g_{LLL}^*, g_{NL}^*) = \text{COV}(g_{LLL}, \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} g_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} g_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} g_{LLL} + g_{NL}) = \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{NL}}, \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{YL}}^* = \text{COV}(g_{LLL}^*, g_{YL}^*) = \text{COV}(g_{LLL}, \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} g_{LLL} + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{NL} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} g_{LLL} + g_{YL}) = \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{NL}} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{YL}}, \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{NL}}^* &= \text{cov}(g_{VL}^*, g_{NL}^*) = \text{cov}(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}g_{LLL} + g_{VL}, \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}g_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}g_{LLL} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}g_{LLL} + g_{NL}) = \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{VL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}^2\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{NL}} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{VL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \sigma_{g_{VL},g_{NL}}, \tag{25}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{YL}}^* &= \text{cov}(g_{VL}^*, g_{YL}^*) = \text{cov}(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}g_{LLL} + g_{VL}, \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}g_{LLL} + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{NL} + \\
&\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{LLL} + g_{YL}) = \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{NL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{VL}} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}^2\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{YL}} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{NL}} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \sigma_{g_{VL},g_{YL}}, \tag{26}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{g_{NL},g_{YL}}^* &= \text{cov}(g_{NL}^*, g_{YL}^*) = \text{cov}(\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}g_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}g_{LLL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}g_{LLL} + \\
&g_{NL}, \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}g_{LLL} + \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{NL} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{VL} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{LLL} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}g_{LLL} + g_{YL}) = \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{NL}} + \\
&\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL}}^2 + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{LLL}} + \\
&\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{YL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{NL}} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{VL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}^2\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{YL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{NL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{VL}} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}^2\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{NL},g_{LLL}} + \\
&\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{NL}}^2 + \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{NL},g_{VL}} + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{NL},g_{LLL}} + \\
&\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL}\sigma_{g_{NL},g_{LLL}} + \sigma_{g_{NL},g_{YL}}. \tag{27}
\end{aligned}$$

The covariances between the residual effects can be estimated in the same way as for genetic effects, therefore, such calculations will be omitted.

The variances between additive genetic effects can be estimated as follows:

$$2(\lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{YL}, g_{NL}}) + 2(\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{YL}, g_{VL}}) + 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{YL}, g_{LLL}}) + 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{NL \rightarrow YL} \sigma_{g_{YL}, g_{LLL}}) + \sigma_{g_{YL}}^2 \quad (31)$$

The variances between the residual effects can be estimated in the same way as for genetic effects, therefore, such calculations will be omitted.

The heritabilities can be estimated as follows:

$$h_{LLL}^{2*} = \frac{\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^{2*}}{\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^{2*} + \sigma_{e_{LLL}}^{2*}} = \frac{\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2}{\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \sigma_{e_{LLL}}^2} \quad (32)$$

$$h_{VL}^{2*} = \frac{\sigma_{g_{VL}}^{2*}}{\sigma_{g_{VL}}^{2*} + \sigma_{e_{VL}}^{2*}} = \frac{\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}^2 \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + 2\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}} + \sigma_{g_{VL}}^2}{\sigma_{g_{VL}}^2 + \sigma_{e_{VL}}^2 + 2\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} (\sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}} + \sigma_{e_{LLL}, g_{VL}}) + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}^2 (\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \sigma_{e_{LLL}}^2)} \quad (33)$$

In the case of h_{NL}^{2*} and h_{YL}^{2*} the heritabilities will be expressed in numerator and denominator separately, as they are very large.

$$h_{NL}^{2*} = \frac{\sigma_{g_{NL}}^{2*}}{\sigma_{g_{NL}}^{2*} + \sigma_{e_{NL}}^{2*}} \quad (34)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{g_{NL}}^{2*} = & \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2 \sigma_{g_{VL}}^2 + 2(\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{VL}, g_{LLL}}) + 2(\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2 \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \sigma_{g_{VL}, g_{LLL}}) + \\ & 2(\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{VL}, g_{NL}}) + 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}}) + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL}^2 \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + \\ & 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2) + 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{NL}}) + 2(\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2 \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}}) + \\ & 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2) + \lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL}^2 \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL}^2 \sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2 + 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{LLL}, g_{VL}}) + \\ & 2(\lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{NL}, g_{VL}}) + 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{NL}, g_{LLL}}) + 2(\lambda_{LLL \rightarrow VL} \lambda_{VL \rightarrow NL} \sigma_{g_{NL}, g_{LLL}}) + \sigma_{g_{NL}}^2 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$r_{g_{LLL},g_{YL}}^* = \frac{\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{YL}}^*}{\sqrt{\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^{2*} \sigma_{g_{YL}}^{2*}}}, \quad (38)$$

$$r_{g_{VL},g_{NL}}^* = \frac{\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{NL}}^*}{\sqrt{\sigma_{g_{VL}}^{2*} \sigma_{g_{NL}}^{2*}}}, \quad (39)$$

$$r_{g_{VL},g_{YL}}^* = \frac{\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{YL}}^*}{\sqrt{\sigma_{g_{VL}}^{2*} \sigma_{g_{YL}}^{2*}}}, \quad (40)$$

$$r_{g_{NL},g_{YL}}^* = \frac{\sigma_{g_{NL},g_{YL}}^*}{\sqrt{\sigma_{g_{NL}}^{2*} \sigma_{g_{YL}}^{2*}}}, \quad (41)$$

The correlations between the residual effects can be estimated in the same way as for genetic effects, therefore, such calculations will be omitted.

Table S10. Genetic parameters estimated from MTM and SEM analyzes

Genetic parameter	MTM	Genetic parameter	SEM
$\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^{2*}$	1.24 (0.67,1.86)	$\sigma_{g_{LLL}}^2$	1.24 (0.67,1.86)
$\sigma_{g_{VL}}^{2*}$	1.05 (0.62,1.51)	$\sigma_{g_{VL}}^2$	1.02 (0.6,1.48)
$\sigma_{g_{NL}}^{2*}$	1.22 (0.77,1.73)	$\sigma_{g_{NL}}^2$	0.25 (0.18,0.33)
$\sigma_{g_{YL}}^{2*}$	1.71 (1.08,2.38)	$\sigma_{g_{YL}}^2$	0.58 (0.38,0.81)
$\sigma_{e_{LLL}}^{2*}$	0.78 (0.56,1.01)	$\sigma_{e_{LLL}}^2$	0.78 (0.56,1.01)
$\sigma_{e_{VL}}^{2*}$	0.61 (0.45,0.79)	$\sigma_{e_{VL}}^2$	0.58 (0.42,0.75)
$\sigma_{e_{NL}}^{2*}$	0.71 (0.53,0.91)	$\sigma_{e_{NL}}^2$	0.14 (0.11,0.17)
$\sigma_{e_{YL}}^{2*}$	1.07 (0.79,1.37)	$\sigma_{e_{YL}}^2$	0.34 (0.26,0.43)
h_{LLL}^{2*}	0.61 (0.45,0.76)	h_{LLL}^2	0.61 (0.45,0.76)
h_{VL}^{2*}	0.63 (0.49,0.76)	h_{VL}^2	0.63 (0.49,0.76)
h_{NL}^{2*}	0.63 (0.51,0.74)	h_{NL}^2	0.65 (0.58,0.72)
h_{YL}^{2*}	0.61 (0.5,0.72)	h_{YL}^2	0.63 (0.52,0.73)
$\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{VL}}^*$	0.24 (-0.11,0.62)	$\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{VL}}$	0.03 (-0.43,0.48)
$\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{NL}}^*$	0.04 (-0.33,0.41)	$\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{NL}}$	-0.01 (-0.16,0.15)
$\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{YL}}^*$	0.13 (-0.3,0.56)	$\sigma_{g_{LLL},g_{YL}}$	-0.05 (-0.37,0.25)
$\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{NL}}^*$	0.99 (0.58,1.46)	$\sigma_{g_{VL},g_{NL}}$	0 (-0.14,0.13)

$\sigma_{gVL,gYL}^*$	0.94 (0.49,1.43)	$\sigma_{gVL,gYL}$	-0.07 (-0.33,0.2)
$\sigma_{gNL,gYL}^*$	1.17 (0.68,1.7)	$\sigma_{gNL,gYL}$	0.02 (-0.07,0.11)
$\sigma_{eLLL,eVL}^*$	0.13 (0,0.28)	$\sigma_{eLLL,eVL}$	0
$\sigma_{eLLL,eNL}^*$	0.01 (-0.14,0.15)	$\sigma_{eLLL,eNL}$	0
$\sigma_{eLLL,eYL}^*$	0.1 (-0.08,0.27)	$\sigma_{eLLL,eYL}$	0
$\sigma_{eVL,eNL}^*$	0.58 (0.41,0.76)	$\sigma_{eVL,eNL}$	0
$\sigma_{eVL,eYL}^*$	0.6 (0.41,0.79)	$\sigma_{eVL,eYL}$	0
$\sigma_{eNL,eYL}^*$	0.71 (0.5,0.93)	$\sigma_{eNL,eYL}$	0
$r_{gLLL,gVL}^*$	0.21 (-0.08,0.5)	$r_{gLLL,gVL}$	0.03 (-0.35,0.4)
$r_{gLLL,gNL}^*$	0.03 (-0.26,0.32)	$r_{gLLL,gNL}$	-0.01 (-0.27,0.25)
$r_{gLLL,gYL}^*$	0.09 (-0.2,0.37)	$r_{gLLL,gYL}$	-0.06 (-0.39,0.28)
$r_{gVL,gNL}^*$	0.87 (0.81,0.93)	$r_{gVL,gNL}$	-0.01 (-0.26,0.25)
$r_{gVL,gYL}^*$	0.7 (0.56,0.83)	$r_{gVL,gYL}$	-0.09 (-0.41,0.24)
$r_{gNL,gYL}^*$	0.81 (0.72,0.9)	$r_{gNL,gYL}$	0.05 (-0.17,0.27)
$r_{eLLL,eVL}^*$	0.19 (0,0.38)	$r_{eLLL,eVL}$	0
$r_{eLLL,eNL}^*$	0.01 (-0.18,0.2)	$r_{eLLL,eNL}$	0
$r_{eLLL,eYL}^*$	0.11 (-0.08,0.29)	$r_{eLLL,eYL}$	0
$r_{eVL,eNL}^*$	0.88 (0.84,0.92)	$r_{eVL,eNL}$	0
$r_{eVL,eYL}^*$	0.72 (0.62,0.82)	$r_{eVL,eYL}$	0
$r_{eNL,eYL}^*$	0.81 (0.75,0.87)	$r_{eNL,eYL}$	0
